

ENHANCING ENERGY ACCESS IN UGANDA'S INDUSTRIAL PARKS: A Data-driven Approach Using Energy Access Explorer

Kasolo Nickson,
kasolo.nickson@gmail.com
Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development, Uganda

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KEYWORDS

- **CCG** - Climate Compatible Growth
- **EAE** – Energy Access Explorer
- **GHI** – Global Horizontal Irradiation
- **ICTP** - International Centre for Theoretical Physics
- **kWh** – Kilowatt per Hour
- **NDP** – National Development Plan
- **SEforALL** - Sustainable Energy for All
- **UIA** – Uganda Investments Authority
- **UETCL** – Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited
- **UK** – United Kingdom

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Executive Summary:

Uganda's industrial parks are vital for the country's economic development but face significant energy challenges, such as unreliable grid connections, inadequate renewable energy integration, and outdated infrastructure. This report uses the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) tool to identify energy access disparities and recommend strategic interventions.

Key findings reveal that industrial parks in high-density areas present more viable opportunities for grid extension and renewable energy deployment. The report recommends targeted grid expansions, renewable energy integrations, and supportive policies to bridge energy gaps and enhance industrial productivity.

Key recommendations include; prioritizing grid expansion for industrial parks located below 30 km from existing transmission infrastructure, Integration of renewable energy solutions to supplement grid energy, and development of incentives to attract private sector investment in industrial park energy projects.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

This report addresses the energy access challenges in Uganda's industrial parks using a data-driven approach with the Energy Access Explorer (EAE) tool. The study's scope includes identification of significant energy access disparities, impact of population density near industrial parks, and proposing energy access solutions to bridge the energy access gaps which will contribute to realisation of Uganda's industrialization goals under Vision 2040 and the National Development Plan III.

1.2 Objective and Aims

The primary objective is to identify the energy access disparities in Uganda's industrial parks and recommend strategic interventions that align with the country's development goals. This includes evaluating the feasibility of grid extension, especially transmission infrastructure, renewable energy integration, and policy support to address existing energy gaps.

2. Methodology

2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool Implemented

The Energy Access Explorer (EAE) tool was utilized to map energy availability, identify access disparities, and assess the feasibility of energy solutions in Uganda's industrial parks. EAE integrates geospatial data to provide a comprehensive view of energy demand and supply factors, facilitating targeted interventions.

2.2 Data Sources

The analysis used data sets as listed below:

- **Geospatial Data**
Locations of industrial parks (UIA) in Uganda.
- **Population Density**

Population density raster data (Bondarenko. et. 2020.) to assess potential energy demand around industrial parks.

- **Grid Infrastructure**

Information on existing transmission lines, and substations (UETCL).

- **Renewable Energy Resources**

Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) data to evaluate solar energy potential (Global Solar Atlas, 2018)

2.3 Assumptions

The analysis is based on the following assumptions:

- **Proximity for grid feasibility:** Industrial parks within 0 to 30 Km km of transmission lines are considered feasible for grid extension. The distribution was excluded due to its challenges, Kiggundu (2019) emphasizes that the aging distribution infrastructure is a major cause of inefficiency and power disruptions.
- **GHI thresholds:** Industrial Parks located in areas with GHI above 2000 kWh/m² are viable for medium and large scale power plants in renewable energy projects.
- **Population density metrics:** Areas with a population density of over 200 people/km² are prioritized for grid extension (*Transmission*).

Scenarios Analysis: The study explores various scenarios considering:

- *Distance from grid infrastructure (Transmission).*
- *Population density variations near industrial parks.*
- *Solar energy potential based on GHI data.*

3.1 Results

3.1 Energy Access Disparities

The analysis identified significant energy access disparities across Uganda's industrial parks:

- **Grid Connectivity:** Three industrial parks are within 1 km of transmission lines, making them prime candidates for immediate grid connection. 3 parks (Iganga, Soroti and Jinja) are within 1 km of transmission lines, 11 parks are 1-4 km away, and 7 parks are 10-50 km from transmission substations.
- **Renewable Energy Potential:** Parks located in areas with high GHI levels (above 2000 kWh/m²) show strong potential for solar energy integration. 7 industrial parks were found to have high renewable energy potential i.e. their location has over 2,000 GHI compared to other industrial park areas.
- **Population Density Impact:** Parks in high-density areas (over 200 people/km²) have more feasible prospects for grid extension. Grid extension is more feasible in high-density areas; 3 parks i.e. Iganga, Soroti and Jinja, are located in areas with 200-5000 people/km², and 11 parks are in low-density areas (<200 people/km²).

3.2 Scenario Analysis

Source: Multi Criteria Analysis from EAE

Figure 2 : Scenario on Grid Energy Access

Figure 1 : Renewable Energy Potential Scenario

Figure 3: Optimal proximity

4. Discussion

4.1 Insights and Implications

The findings underscore the importance of strategic energy planning tailored to the specific conditions of each industrial park. High-density areas near existing grid infrastructure should be prioritized for transmission grid expansion, while parks in remote or low-density areas may benefit more from decentralized renewable energy solutions.

4.2 Recommendations

- **Renewable Energy Deployment:** Given Uganda's high solar potential especially in the east and north of the country, renewable energy access solutions like solar energy should be deployed in parks where grid extension is not feasible.
- **Policy and Investment Support:** The government should formulate subsidy-oriented policies to attract private investments in renewable energy projects tailored to industrial parks.

4.3 Limitations

The case study analysis did not account for cost benefit analysis and future changes in energy access demand due to industrial growth or technological advancements.

4.4 Future Research

Future studies should explore research on the implementation challenges and the economic impacts of proposed energy solutions, and the development of more integrated and inclusive energy planning. This includes the importance of coordinating a working group for an EAE sustainability plan and continuous data collection among members.

Organization	Sector	Responsibility	Member/s
Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development	Government	Oversee energy policies and grid expansion through ensuring alignment with Vision 2040 and NDP III.	Energy planners, policy makers
Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited (UETCL)	Energy Transmission	Extend and upgrade transmission lines, integration of renewable energy sources.	Engineers, grid management specialists
Uganda Industrial Research Institute (UIRI)	Institutions	Conduct research on industrial energy needs, support capacity building and model improvement.	Researchers, technical staff
Renewable Energy Associations	Private Sector	Promote private sector investment in renewable energy for industrial parks, assist in renewable data management.	Investors, renewable energy experts
Universities & Educational Institutions	Academic & Research Institution	Incorporate EAE tool into curricula, lead workshops on sustainable energy access management.	Academics, students.

National Planning Authority (NPA)	Government	Develop long-term energy and industrialization strategies and sustainability.	Planners.
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5. Conclusion

The Energy Access Explorer tool is instrumental in identifying and addressing energy access disparities in Uganda's industrial parks. The study highlights the need for a tailored approach to energy planning, focusing on grid expansion in high-density areas and renewable energy deployment in more remote locations.

The analysis of Uganda's industrial parks reveals that regions with higher solar irradiance (GHI) and low population density, such as those farther from existing grid infrastructure, are more suited for renewable energy solutions, particularly solar power. These regions face significant challenges in extending the grid due to high costs and low economic returns, making them ideal candidates for solar energy deployment.

This differentiation in energy potential across regions is a pivotal in formulation of policies for targeted investments i.e. policymakers should prioritize renewable energy development in regions with high GHI to optimize resource use, while focusing grid expansion efforts on high-density areas where grid extension is economically viable. This approach will ensure efficient allocation of resources and also support reliable and sustainable energy access, aligning with Uganda's Vision 2040 and National Development Plan III objectives.

6. Recommendations

- **Grid expansion:** Major emphasis should be concentrated on industrial parks located within feasible distances from existing infrastructure for immediate grid connection especially transmission facilities.
- **Integration of renewable energy access:** Through development and implementation of solar energy solutions in industrial parks where grid extension is challenging especially in areas far away from transmission facilities and with less population density.
- **Conducive policy development and implementation:** Create supportive policies and incentives to attract private investment in energy infrastructure within industrial parks.

References

- World Bank, 2022. <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator>. World Bank Group.
- D. Mentis, Lily Odarno, Davida Wood, F. Jendle, Elise Mazur, Anila Qehaja, F.Gassert.(2019). Energy Access Explorer : Data and Methods. World Resources Institute
- Energy Sector GIS Working Group Uganda, 2017. www.energy-gis.ug Accessed through Energy Access Explorer,. www.energyaccessexplorer.org.
- Government of Uganda, 2020. *National Development Plan III (NDP III)*. Kampala: Government of Uganda.
- UBOS, 2024. *Uganda National Population Census report*. Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS),

- ERA, 2023. *ERA Statistical Bulletin, ESI Performance report*. Electricity Regulatory Authority (ERA)
- UIA, 2024. *www.uia.go.ug*. Uganda Investment Authority (UIA).
- Bondarenko M., Kerr D., Sorichetta A., and Tatem, A.J. 2020. Census/projection-disaggregated gridded population datasets, adjusted to match the corresponding UNPD 2020 estimates, for 51 countries across sub-Saharan Africa using building footprints. WorldPop, University of Southampton, UK. doi:10.5258/SOTON/WP00683 <https://ciesin.columbia.edu/data/hrsl/> Accessed through Energy Access Explorer, [date]. www.energyaccessexplorer.org.
- Global Solar Atlas. 2018. Retrieved from <http://globalsolaratlas.info/>. Accessed through Energy Access Explorer, . www.energyaccessexplorer.org.
- Kiggundu, J. (2019). "Challenges of Aging Infrastructure in Uganda's Power Distribution Network."

